

SAY, WHAT DID YOU SEE? A QUALITATIVE INTERVIEW REVEALS HOW USERS INTERPRETED GUI ICONS

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ABSTRACT

A comprehensive user test was conducted with 29 participants, 11 of whom were aged five to twelve. The intention of the exploratory computer-based test was to collect both quantitative and qualitative information—this article reviews the qualitative data only. After the user test, each participant answered identical, open-ended questions regarding his/her approach(es) to the task. Data was split into <13 (Youths) and >17 (Adults). The age groups' responses are compared: Youths' responses were often succinct, direct, and confident compared with the long, detailed, and verbose responses from the Adults. Adults often contradicted themselves whereas Youths did not. In order to categorize the participants' diverse experiences, responses were analyzed for target words. The potential for design biases is highlighted. It is recommended that designers verbally test their specific user group—often—during the HCI/GUI design process in order to avoid designing from their own perspective and misunderstanding their user group entirely.

KEYWORDS: *Human-computer interaction, GUI design, user test, computer icons, visual design bias*

INTRODUCTION

This exploratory research focuses on how people interpret computerized visual stimulation. In this case, on-screen icons are the subject of investigation. The approach involves asking participants to view a fixed set of icons and collecting their responses, and determining if any patterns arise from the data. Of particular interest is if users respond that certain aspects of visual design are more influential than others (e.g. contrast, color, photorealism, perspective, number of metaphors, adherence to archetype, etc.). It seems logical that the more elements we are presented with onscreen, the more we are required to visually 'digest' those elements; and vast data in the field of attention has confirmed this. Two research groups say it well: 'Our environment contains much more sensory information than we can process at any given time' (Liu & Mance, 2011, p26), and 'people can respond to only a small amount of the sensory information present at any moment' (Corbetta et al., 1990, p. 1556). Visual processing takes valuable time and energy, especially when the extra visual elements are redundant and unnecessary. In this era where computers are becoming increasingly entwined in our everyday lives, our visual sense is immersed in ever-increasing amounts of stimuli. There surely must be a saturation point

somewhere. Due to these factors, it becomes even more important for HCI/GUI designers to use streamlined visual interfaces to reduce cognitive load, reduce the potential for stress and increase a user's effectiveness when s/he interacts with a computerized device. In short, this researcher ascertains that visual information should be as simple and effective as possible in all human-computer interface tools.

Several studies support the use of simple visual design over complicated visual design: Chiu et al. (2012); Davis & Swezey (1983); Huang et al. (2002); Gittins (1986); McDougall et al. (2000); McDougall & Reppa (2008); Reppa et al. (2008); Yan (2011) etc. Byrne sums it up:

for icons to be effective aids to visual search, they must be simple and easily discriminable ...

They (icons) seem to clutter the display with information that participants are unable to employ to their advantage (Byrne, 1993).

There is a large amount of research regarding how icons affect the participant's experience and how to design icons effectively. However, these studies do not distinguish between all age groups. Studies with adults and seniors are prevalent, whereas studies comparing adults with children are virtually absent. This is not a good idea as children/youth's

computer experience is continuously on the rise (Rocheleau, 1995). Children and youths represent an important participant group (Chiasson, & Gutwin, 2005), and it is important that their needs be taken into account (Druin, 1999). Not all user groups are included regularly, despite such acknowledgments from researchers (e.g. Adams et al):

Within HCI, there is also the recognition that the focus on tasks is not enough to design and implement an effective system. There is also a growing need to understand how user issues are subjectively and collectively experienced and perceived by different user groups (Adams et al., 2008, p. 138)

This article describes one data set of a computer-based user test that incorporated both quantitative (via participant ranking) and qualitative (via post-test interview) techniques. According to Adams et al. (2008), this multiple approach (i.e. gathering numerous sets of data simultaneously) embodies the true intention of grounded theory research. The user test was conducted in a modern computer laboratory setting (Jensen & Skov, 2005) where conventional computer-interface icons were used as an example of low-level visual stimuli. ‘Low-level’ in this context refers to the icons’ relatively small size and apparently limited amount of two-dimensional visual information. This researcher considers computer-based icons as anything but visually limited—they are miniature, independent visual compositions. The research behind this article investigates the independent (albeit small) nature of computer icons’ visual composition, not their meta-level position within applications or on the screen itself.

GUI designers face numerous challenges while designing apparently humble little compositions such as the computer icon. The question at the root of the design process is: What are the primary visual factors that GUI designers must control? A large body of literature attests to the importance of considering numerous aspects (‘parameters’) of the icon’s visual design. Näsänen & Ojanpää (2003) found that contrast affects the speed of icon interpretation—the speed by which icons can be searched for—was clearly dependent on image contrast at small values, but relatively independent at high contrast values. Lindberg & Näsänen (2003) found that although icon spacing does not have an effect on search times, the size of the interface elements has a great effect. Huang (2007) showed that four visual variables significantly affected search performance: figure/background color combinations, type of computer icon, figure/background area ratio. Skogen (forthcoming) found that there are age differences in how simple and complicated icons are interpreted. In fact, interpretation of an icon appeared to be completely contradictory in many cases. Although there is abundant research regarding icons’ visual parameters and how to design them, there is a lack of research on how these visual design parameters are interpreted by children/youths. Indeed, numerous HCI design studies use adults as test participants—as stated above, adults do not represent the full spectrum of computer users.

From a study from Skogen (forthcoming), Youths <thirteen years old seemed to recognize the detail-rich and highly realistic icons faster than the abstracted, rectilinear ones,

based upon their ranking of those icons first (equivalent to the “pickup order” described in Skogen, 2006). Adults responded initially to the icons that showed fewer details. Although there were no participants to demonstrate it, there appeared to be a shift between ages thirteen and seventeen, after which users began to respond similarly to the Adults. From this, we can deduce that the descriptors associated with the terms ‘simple’ and ‘complicated’ do not apply to all participant groups.

For this user test, participants of varying age groups did not interpret GUI icons in the same manner.

At the end of the user test, participants took a short post-test verbal interview intended to give them an opportunity to discuss, explain and/or clarify the criteria they thought about and the strategies they employed during the test. The fundamental point of the short, open-ended qualitative interview revolved around how participants interpret the visual icons. The study was exploratory, lacked a formal hypothesis, and gathered quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously. The fundamental purpose for the post-test qualitative interview was to gather verbatim information regarding:

- What particular words did participants use to a.) Describe their approach(es); b.) Describe the criteria they thought about; and/or c.) Describe the strategies that they used to rank the icons?

This final research topic forms the basis of this article.

METHOD

This exploratory user test was conducted at the National Center for Patient Journal Research computer lab at St. Olav’s hospital, Trondheim, Norway. The equipment was conventional: a modern Microsoft PC with mouse and flat screen sat at a standard table with a comfortable chair. The room was airy, uncluttered, quiet and well lit (with windows to a natural setting outside). The test environment was intentionally set up to represent a basic computer room that a participant might have at home. Participants were given an identical set of instructions on a sheet of paper (to ensure consistency), which asked them to view sets of icons on a computer screen. If the participant was too young to read, then a parent read it for them.

The computer test included a set of icons (ten sets in total), where each set of icons represented one theme: e.g. *Home*, *PC*, and *Trash*. The icon sets were (in order): *Search*, *Edit*, *Document*, *Mouse*, *Mail*, *Home*, *Print*, *Book*, *Trash*, *PC*. This set (including its specific sequencing) was intended to duplicate the format of the pilot study (Skogen, 2006), with one major change: this user test would be conducted in the computer icons’ native media, the computer. However, unlike the pilot study, this user test included two extra categories (*Search* and *Edit*) at the beginning. This gave the participant time to become familiar with the test format, so that when they encountered the original eight categories (i.e. *Document* – *PC*),

participants were seated comfortably, accustomed to computer/mouse's functionality, and familiar with the user test's format and progression. Each participant completed the user test individually, while the researcher was present at all times, seated discreetly to the side and behind. This provided the participant with a sense of security—the researcher was available for questions (particularly with the younger participants) and silently took notes. Although the researcher's presence may have influenced the users' responses, this is impossible to know. They said afterwards that they were undisturbed by her presence, and most participants stated that they'd forgotten she was there.

For each icon set, the participant saw eight icons of one theme appear on the screen at one time (see Fig. 1 below). The test consisted of ten sets/themes of icons, eight icons per set. The set of icons appeared in a circular format as shown below (Fig. 1). When the user was finished with one theme, s/he pressed *Next* to bring up the next theme. Time was not recorded and there was no time limit. To avoid potential bias due to an icon's placement in the circle, the computer repositioned the icons randomly with every reload. This means that each participant saw the icons in a randomized, unique relationship to each other, yet always in the same circular format. The other elements on the screen (instructional text, scale, button placement) remained constant for all participants. The participant was instructed to drag-and-drop each icon to one box on the scale. Each box could contain only one icon.

After completing the ranking for a set, the participant moved to the next icon theme by clicking '*Next*', whereupon the next circular set of icons appeared immediately. Participants were encouraged to respond quickly, not to think too much, and to trust their first reaction. Three types of data were collected for each participant:

1. Ranking of the icons (for quantitative data collection)
2. Video recording of the test in progress, with permission (for later reference/review)
3. Post-test interview responses for categorization purposes (for qualitative data collection)

The video apparatus was mounted very clearly on the top of the computer screen. Each participant granted permission to record prior to the test. The researcher's role was to be available as a 'guide' during the test, unobtrusive yet available. She served to help with computer formalities only, and avoided influencing any answers of the test itself. Only a few of the participants needed her assistance at all.

Quantitative Data—Participants Rank the Icons

As stated earlier, the quantitative results (Skogen, forthcoming) revealed an unforeseen age difference: detail-rich icons termed *Complicated* were often ranked lower on the scale (i.e. closer to *Simple*) for the Youths. The Adults responded in a predictable way, however the Youths did not. The results imply that designers unwittingly carry inherent biases regarding how icons and their visual parameters appear to various users across all age groups. It appears that one design does not fit all, and designers should not presume that they do. This will be discussed in the section, 'Discussion' below.

Qualitative Data—Post-Test Interview

The researcher spoke the native language of the participant (English or Norwegian), and each participant responded in his/her native language. The intention of the post-test interview was to gather participants' descriptive words regarding (in order of importance):

Figure 1. "PC" themed-icons: a screenshot from the user test

- a. The criteria and strategies each participant used to rank the icons
- b. How each participant defined the words “Simple” and “Complicated”
- c. Closing the test in an appropriate & natural manner (rather than the participant leaving the room immediately).

The five Open-Ended Interview Questions were (in order):

1. Did you enjoy the test?
2. Can you describe the criteria and/or strategies you used to place the icons—what did you think about?
Rephrased for the Youths: How did you choose where each icon should go—what did you think about?
3. How did you define *Simple* and *Complicated*?
4. Did you find anything particularly easy or difficult?
5. When asked to think of one single icon from the test, which one comes to mind?

At the end of the test, the participants often pushed their chair back and paused... some of them had used only four minutes to take the entire test so they were slightly out of breath. The difference between Youths’ and Adults’ responses began to appear at this moment of test completion: almost all of the Adults started talking immediately upon finishing the test, whereas all the Youths looked quietly back towards the researcher and waited for instructions on what to do next. Regarding the answers themselves, very often the Adults’ responses were obtuse and self-contradictory. For the Adults, the researcher frequently needed to prompt the participant to be more specific in his/her response, give examples, or try to describe more clearly what they were thinking. Regarding question two, the Adults often answered in a confusing or wordy manner, almost as if they were trying to impress the researcher. Youths responded very directly and concisely. This also will be addressed in detail in the section ‘Discussion’ below.

ANALYSIS

Limits of Language

It is important to recognize that everything—including open-ended responses—is open to interpretation.

By the very act of using language, a person already filters the type of information that their mind’s eye can see.

This phenomenon can be described with an example from an eight year old’s responses to the interview questions. When asked which icon he recalled from the test, he said ‘the computer’. When asked ‘Which one?’, he answered, ‘The one that looks like a simple one!’ In his mind’s eye, he knew exactly which one he was talking about, but the nature of linguistics prevented this researcher from understanding which one he meant. Language is a crude tool for seeing into another person’s inner thoughts. This is contrary to Munslow’s postulate that:

History owes its very nature to the fact that language is an incredibly rich medium for describing and explaining the meaning of objects in the world. (Narrative and History - Theory and History. James, 2007, p.34).

Categories

For analysis of the five Open-Ended Questions, we used grounded-theory techniques described by Bryant et al. (2007); Charmaz (2006); Clarke & Friese (2007); and Seale et al., (ed.) (2004). Kvale & Brinkman (2009) provided numerous helpful tips on interviewing techniques in general. Ryghaug (2002) offers a nice outline of various methods of text analysis, including structuralism, semiotics, and ‘linguistic-based analysis methods’, but she does not go into specific detail regarding exactly how to do it.

As per the quantitative data set (Skogen, forthcoming), verbal responses were first split into two age groups: <13 (Youths) and >17 (Adults). This was done to maintain consistency across both sets of data.

For the qualitative/interview data set, analysis began with dividing all responses into two major groups, ‘Criteria’ and ‘Strategy’. Criteria was regarded as noun-based and referred to ‘what’ the user did, whereas *Strategy* was more verb-based and referred to ‘how’ the user did it. After this division, words were allowed to rise out of the two groups. Although seemingly diverse, participants’ responses showed that common words were often used (regardless of native language). All responses were analyzed, and sorted according to those word commonalities. These commonalities quickly revealed ‘target words’: i.e. words that arose more often than other descriptors. Upon scoring of the target words, the titles of the categories became evident. The specificity of the target words grew outward to encompass the words that participants (collectively) had used to describe a particular visual parameter of the icons. These target words were then codified into larger categories.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Emotional Value of Responses

After documentation of every word of the post-test interview, the emotional value of the responses became noticeable, based upon age. The Youths displayed an unassuming self-confidence, chose direct words, and answered the questions bluntly, sometimes monosyllabically. Adults often (but not always) responded in a verbose, complicated manner, and their answers were sometimes self-contradicting or did not make sense at all. The Youths answered the question, without pause or second thought, and then waited for the next—they responded to the open-ended questions very clearly. Not once during the Youth’s interviews did the researcher sense an awkward pause, yet this was almost common with the Adults.

During the interview, it was important to avoid offering deeper clarification of the five Interview Questions due to:

1. Need to maintain consistency
2. Not wanting to impose vocabulary upon the participant
3. Avoidance of leading questions.

On a few occasions the researcher was compelled to expand upon the questions, but this only occurred in the rare instances where the extended pause felt too awkward for both the participant and the researcher. In these cases, she repeated the question, with slight rewording and/or encouragement to continue. For the few instances where it did happen, it occurred only with Adults. With the Youths, there was no need to clarify.

There were no pauses where the Youths seemed to fail to understand the question, nor did the Youths hesitate or take time to prepare an answer. This shows yet another level of age differences between *Simple* (i.e. Youths') and *Complicated* (i.e. Adults') responses. The researcher was often caught off guard by the Youths' verbal responses because there was no way to be prepared for the succinctness and clarity of their answers. Due to the Youths' concise, clear, direct answers, the interviews with the Youths went very quickly. Although she realized the Youths responded effectively at the time, it was not possible to fully experience the Youths' confident directness until she analyzed their videoed responses.

Contrarily, some of the Adults' descriptions of their criteria, strategies, and other answers seemed to flow into each other, and for some participants, answers became almost interchangeable. Even upon review of the videos, some of the Adults' sentences were convoluted to the point that it was difficult to discern what they were trying to say. Indeed, categorizing the use of language proved to be more difficult than anticipated. Still, the words were tallied and specific usage was documented. The words were important, and the general communicability of the participants' answers did not affect the categorization. However, it served as an interesting observation (between Youths and Adults) only.

Categories

i. Color

The target word '*color/farge*' came up often, and there didn't seem to be another word that participants used to communicate that particular aspect of the icons' design. One 9-year-old pinpointed *color* (while simultaneously using the word *simple/enkel* on two occasions):

...det var noe med enkelte som jeg likte veldig godt. Jeg likte dem med farger.

Farger var litt enklere.

(There was something about the simple ones that I liked very much. I liked those with color. Color was a little more simple.)

COLOR became one of the codified categories because the participants used it often. However, as the quantitative/rank-

ing data from this user test revealed, there may be an inherent bias lurking in the use of the word 'color'. Some participants had very different interpretations of color: a few participants decided icons were *Simple* because they contained color, whereas other participants decided that icons were *Complicated* because they contained color. Those who said color made an icon *Complicated*, also said that black & white icons were more *Simple* than the colored ones. Regardless, it was only the Youths who considered color to be a simplifying parameter (perhaps making the icon appear more realistic). Contrarily, the Adults considered color to be a more complicating parameter. This disparity in interpretation of this one parameter—COLOR—between Youths and Adults is perhaps one of the most important results of this study.

ii. Recognizability

Many participants described another parameter of the icons' visual impression: its ability to communicate meaning quickly—it's recognizability. This refers to an icons' ability to represent what it was supposed to represent, i.e. whether it was easy/difficult to understand what the icon described. The terms used for this became coded as RECOGNIZABILITY.

iii. Detail

Many participants described the icons' richness of detail, which quickly became coded as DETAIL.

Again, target words were easy to identify due to '*detail*' being used in a consistent manner. Only one person mentioned '*perspective*', while another person mentioned '*photorealism*' only once.

iv. Degree of Abstraction

Many participants found it difficult to describe the concept of visual simplicity without using the word 'simple'.

From this user test (particularly the quantitative data herein) we may deduce that each participant carries an individualized idea of what 'simple design' means, and this term's interpretive emotional value might be linked to the user's age. Simplicity appears to be in the eyes of the beholder. Indeed, a 'simple' icon means something different when viewed from an Adult's viewpoint when compared with a Youth's or a child's viewpoint. This researcher states: the presumption that 'simple' means lack of detail is inherently biased and implies that an adult's viewpoint is the only one that exists. McDougall showed that an icon's concreteness (i.e. the extent to which icons pictorially represent objects, places, or people) primarily affects the grasp of meaning (McDougall et al., 2000), as well as correlates strongly with the ease of an icon's interpretation (McDougall et al., 2006). For this study, the concept of concreteness became expanded and termed as DEGREE of ABSTRACTION.

All of the categories can very easily meld into each other, yet Adult participants seemed to switch quickly between two specific categories, DETAIL and DEGREE of ABSTRACTION.

This quick switching could even occur mid-sentence. One adult participant stated: ‘Line drawings are easier than photorealistic ones and less items makes it easier, makes it simpler’. This participant felt he needed to elaborate on his first sentence (DETAIL) by supporting it with another (DEGREE of ABSTRACTION). Although DETAIL and DEGREE of ABSTRACTION can easily overlap, this researcher intends to keep them separate as much as possible.

Other Creative Descriptors

Some descriptions did not fit into any categorical sorting, yet they became interesting because of their insightfulness and uniqueness. One unforgettable example came from the youngest participant (five years old):

I think the simpler things are harder to break.

The most simple things are the most hard to break, they are!

This was such a profoundly new and unpredicted approach to the task, that it took a few moments to actually comprehend it. Imagine a category entitled Breakability! This participant was a big, strong five-year-old, who (his mother mentioned later) was prone to breaking his toys, so this made perfect sense to him—this ideology of breakability fit into his world seamlessly. He was accustomed to it.

Historicity. A second example is the thirteen-year-old who used a unique technique—historical reference—to determine his definition of *Simple/Complicated*. He was the only one who did so:

Enkle var de som var historiske... kompliserte var moderne.

(Simple were those that were historical, Complicated were modern.)

Replicability. When one eleven-year-old was asked what he thought about during the test, he responded:

Det jeg tenkte på var hvis du skal lage... tegne de tingene der... hvor lang tid skal du ta?

(What I thought about was if you were to make...draw those things there...how long would it take?)

This participant’s strategy had been to convert each icon into an estimation of his time required to replicate it by drawing it. This idea was actually conveyed by two of the youths, completely independent of each other. This participant was eleven years old and the other individual who used this approach was seventeen years old. Unfortunately this study did not include enough participants to determine how likely would it be for an adult to employ a similar strategy. A criteria/strategy could become its own category if there were enough respondents to support it.

Finally, three of the Adults (all female) strategically interpreted how the icons would appear to others. This was unique among the Adults... none of the Youths used this tactic.

The final four categories were:

1. COLOR
2. RECOGNIZABILITY

3. DETAIL
4. DEGREE of ABSTRACTION

Icon Recall

The fifth Interview Question asked for the participant to recall one specific icon from the test. The intention here was to see which icon made enough of an impression to remain memorable beyond the conclusion of the test. Interestingly, there was only one icon that was recalled by more than one participant (five in total: four Adults and one Youth). It was a highly unusual, detailed and colorful rendering of a house (‘home’). It was also the icon deemed most ‘Complicated’ by all Adults. Table one below shows the icon with its corresponding ranking scores for both Adults and Youths (on a scale of 1=Simple to 8=Complicated).

	ADULTS (>16)	YOUTHS (<13)	ALL AGES COMBINED
 Home	7.6	4.8	6.4

Table 1. The most-recalled icon with ranking scores

All other participants recalled only one instance of other icons.

CONCLUSION

In describing the criteria used to rank the icons, participants in this user test revealed numerous strategies regarding what they thought about while ranking the icons on a scale of *Simple-Complicated*. Some participants used unique and highly insightful approaches whereas the majority showed commonalities among their responses. The fact that we could identify, group, and extract four categories from those target words shows that there were similar approaches to interpreting the icons. Although people used the same target words, (e.g. COLOR), this does *not* infer they interpreted or defined that word similarly.

This is the most important point of the qualitative aspect of this user test, perhaps the largest contribution: designers cannot presume that users will see their designs in the exact same manner. This study showed that there appeared to be age and individual differences in how people interpreted the visual parameter of COLOR. As this one example shows, the viewer’s definitions might be contradictory. If this is the case, how many other visual parameters do we misjudge? It is important for those involved with computer interface design to know the potential for this discrepancy among their users.

This user test incorporated a small sample size (n=29) and although all ages were not represented, it does accomplish a very important task for GUI/HCI designers: it highlights the potential for inherent biases. As adults, we tend to design

from our own perspective, and this means that our designs potentially carry a quiet, unintentional bias. We presume that our definitions of the numerous aspects of visual design apply equally to all age groups (children, adults, and seniors, across cultural boundaries), while this study shows that such presumptions may be highly incorrect.

Designing from one's own adult perspective is a trap into which many GUI designers fall. The only way to avoid this trap is to test the user group repeatedly to ensure that it is the user group's interpretation of the design that is being met, not the designer's. In order to avoid this pitfall, a GUI designer must test often, particularly during the beginning phases of the design process. The most effective time to test is as early as possible, when design changes are easily made. Otherwise, a designer has the potential to miss his/her target user group entirely. Repeated user testing, during *all* phases of the design process, is the only insurance that the designer has—it's the only way s/he can be sure to meet the needs of the intended user group. According to Thomson (2008, p.1):

Indeed, the perspectives of children and young people are of interest to contemporary social scientists precisely because they offer specific and unique insights...which can easily slip below the horizons of older inquirers. The omission of these perspectives can easily lead to researchers making interpretations and representations that are very shortsighted and which miss the point.

This study shows that youths' do not share the same visual design needs for GUI/HCI applications as adults. In addition, people's interpretation of visual information changes as we age. It appears that a GUI icon's visual design—its simplicity and/or visual complexity—is in the eye of the beholder.

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